

About the law of black radiation; by M. Thiesen.

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Keywords: Black radiation, blackbody, Quantum Physics

Abstract

This article is a faithful translation of Thiesen's original publication from 1900: "*Über das Gesetz der schwarzen Strahlung; von M. Thiesen.*" where he gives the generic formula used by Max Planck to demonstrate his Law.

No translation found on the Internet respects the original form. We offer this translated version for students or amateurs wishing to understand or discover the origins of Planck's law and Quantum physics.

About the law of black radiation;

by M. Thiesen.

(Presented at the meeting of February 2, 1900.)

(Compare above p. 87.)

KIRCHHOFF used the concept of the (entirely) black body in 1862; simultaneously, he showed how the radiation emitted by such a body could be realized independently of the existence of a genuinely black body.¹⁾ Since then, it has become customary to consider radiation independently of the body that emits it, and it is, therefore, advisable to give the radiation that has the properties of that emitted by a black body itself a particular name, most simply as black radiation; the paradox of the expression disappears on closer inspection since we cannot reconcile the trivial and scientific concepts of blackness.²⁾

KIRCHHOFF showed that the energy of black radiation at a given absolute temperature T was a particular function of the wavelength; we will use $E d\lambda$ to denote the radiant energy, which covers the wavelengths between λ and $d\lambda$. The law of black radiation is known as soon as E is a function of T .

The first important step towards the theoretical derivation of this law was taken by Mr. BOLTZMANN³⁾ by proving that the total radiation, i.e., the following quantity, is proportional to the fourth power of the absolute temperature:

$$\int_0^{\infty} E d\lambda$$

1) G. KIRCHHOFF, Ges. Treatise. P. 597.

2) You can e.g. B. claim that in a dark room black bodies are lighter than white or colored ones.

3) L. BOLTZMANN, Wied. Ann. 22. S. 31 u. 291. 1881.

Next went Mr. W. Wien, ¹⁾ which determined the change that each wavelength undergoes due to a specific increase in total energy.

In connection with Boltzmann's law, WIEN's law leads to the expression

$$1. \quad E = T^5 \psi[\lambda T],$$

where ψ is an as-yet-unknown function. However, the derivation of this law given by Mr. WIEN is not perfect; ²⁾ However, the objections to this can easily be eliminated using a different formulation.

This Wien's Law is of great importance. First, one reduces the function E of two variables to the function of only one variable; the radiation is therefore completely known if it is given, for example, for a specific temperature but for all wavelengths or all temperatures at one wavelength. In addition, the law indicates the existence of two natural constants, which depend only on the unit of temperature and on the three mechanical units; in conjunction with the speed of light and the constant of the law of attraction, one obtains a natural measure of temperature and mechanical units that is independent of the nature of a particular body.

1) W. WIEN, Berl. Meeting area P. 55. 1893 and again. Ann. 52. P. 132. 1894 The wording of the law given here is missing from WIEN.

2) Mr. WIEN adopts the simplification of the observation, which is not readily permissible here, by decomposing the radiation into three mutually perpendicular directions. It seems to me that an inaccuracy introduced by this is compensated for by a peculiar consideration, which is based on the unsubstantiated assumption that a quantity which by its nature, as a ratio of two quantities that can be set independently to be infinitely small, must remain indeterminate, as infinite is to be assumed large.

Mr. PLANCK explained this as a more specific form of the radiation law that one can mention immediately, but it also applies to the general form. Then, as can easily be seen, there cannot be a simple power, so a natural constant of the dimensions of the argument xT must exist; BOLTZMANN's law already gives the second constant.

The function Ψ must satisfy certain conditions, which are most accessible to fulfill if one set:

$$2. \quad \Psi[x] = \Psi_m \left(\frac{x_m}{x} e^{1 - \frac{x_m}{x}} \right)^\alpha ; 5 > \alpha > 2$$

Ψ_m and x_m are the two natural constants, denoting the most significant value the function achieves for $x = x_m$. Mr. WIEN ²⁾ tried to justify this formula with the particular value $\alpha = 5$; Another derivation, which also leads to $\alpha = 5$, was given by Mr. PLANCK. ³⁾ The more general formula would follow from an empirical formula established by Mr. PASCHEN ⁴⁾ for the (non-black) radiation of various bodies through connection with WIEN's law; but Mr. PASCHEN found α to be noticeably larger than 5 on average.

As Mr. LUMMER and PRINGSHEIM ⁵⁾ reported, their experiments indeed confirmed the WIEN's displacement law given by 1., but show systematic deviations from the WIEN-PLANCK's distribution law (formula 2. for $\alpha = 5$).

1) M. PLANCK, Meeting area. d. Berl. And. S. 440, 1899 in Ann. d. Phys. 1 S. 69, 1900.

2) W. WIEN, Wied. Ann. 58 S. 662, 1896.

3) M. PLANCK a. a. O. Mr. PLANCK has now promised an addition to his initially not complete proof.

4) F. PASCHEN, Wied. Ann, 58 S 487, Formel D. 1896.

5) O. LUMMER and E. PRINGSHEIM Verh. d. Deutsch. Phys. Ges. 1. S. 215, 1899.

One now occasionally found, first using the published diagram and then more precisely from the original figures that the gentlemen kindly shared, that the experiments are reproduced very well by formula 2. as soon as one set $\alpha = 4.5$. Mr. BECKMANN's experiments discussed by Mr. RUBENS ¹⁾ confirm this result and subsequently became even more likely by the experiments ²⁾ carried out by Mr. LUMMER and PRINGSHEIM for large wavelengths.

As pointed out above, it remains to modify the proof of WIEN's displacement law.

In space ν , suitable walls enclose radiation of density $\mathcal{S}$, of which the wavelength (more precisely, the wavelength between λ and $\lambda + d\lambda$) comes from the part $E[\lambda] d\lambda$. With the dispersion of the radiation, if any inequalities arise, the radiation should immediately be made wholly dispersed by the walls.

In the space, the plate f moves in the direction of its normal with the speed $y' = \beta v$; here y' is the speed of light, β is a small quantity.

We now select a wave train with a specific direction. This direction should form the angle ϑ with the direction of the plate's movement and determine it by the azimuthal angle φ . We also introduce ϑ_1 and v_1 , which denote the apparent direction and speed of the wave movement towards the plate, and use $c = \cos\vartheta$, $c_1 = \cos\vartheta_1$ for the abbreviation.

Then the density of the energy of the wave train specialized in this way is $\frac{1}{4\pi} E[\lambda] d\lambda dc d\varphi$ and the volume that contains the radiation of this type, which falls on the surface f of the plate in the time element, is $\mp v_1 c_1 dt$. One, therefore, gets for the Energy of this kind striking the plate:

$$\mp \frac{1}{4\pi} f v_1 dt E[\lambda] d\lambda c_1 dc d\varphi$$

Alternatively, if we sum for φ :

$$\mp \frac{1}{2} f v_1 dt E[\lambda] d\lambda c_1 dc$$

1) H. RUBENS, Wied. Ann. 69. S. 576. 1899.

2) Presented at the meeting on February 2nd this year.

This energy now undergoes the following changes. According to DOPPLER's principle, it transforms the wavelength of the radiation from λ into

$$\lambda \frac{1+\beta c}{1-\beta c},$$

by reflection from the plate, which we imagine to be regularly reflective for a somewhat more straightforward calculation. In addition, the plate experiences a pressure which, according to MAXWELL, in the direction of the radiation is equal to but twice as much as the reflected radiation. The work done by radiation density when the radiation is absorbed as the plate moves increases the energy, at least in a first approximation, by $-fy' dt \cdot c^2 \cdot E[\lambda] d\lambda dc$.

We now assume that the moving plate closes off the space and neglects higher powers of β ; furthermore, we assume c_1 to be positive. It then becomes $dv = fy' dt$.

We can now summarize: From the originally existing energy

$$v E[\lambda] d\lambda \text{ has the part } \frac{1}{2} \frac{dv}{\beta} E[\lambda] d\lambda c_1 dc_1$$

its wavelength is increased by $2\beta\lambda c_1$, the average increase in wavelength is, therefore,

$$d\lambda = \frac{dv}{v} \lambda \int_0^1 c_1^2 dc_1 = \frac{dv}{3v} \lambda.$$

At the same time, the density of the energy was changed relatively by adding the energy:

$$- \frac{dv}{in} \int_0^1 c_1^2 dc_1 = - \frac{1}{3} \frac{dv}{in}$$

But also by changing the volume by

$$- \frac{dv}{v}$$

together therefore by

$$\frac{dS}{S} = - \frac{1}{3} \frac{dv}{v}$$

Let us add BOLTZMANN's law, which one can easily derive from the basics obtained:

$$\frac{dS}{S} = 4 \frac{dT}{T}$$

So, in the following relationship, one obtains WIEN's displacement law:

$$0 = \frac{d\lambda}{\lambda} + \frac{dT}{T}$$

If the plate does not close off the space or move back and forth by equal amounts, one gets a wavelength dispersion (in a first approximation without changing the energy). However, to a first approximation, any radiation for which $E[\lambda]$ is a continuous function remains unchanged; one cannot obtain a new condition for the form of black radiation in this way.

Acknowledgments

Thanks, especially for the help of the volunteers in the science section of the Wikipedia reference desk, for their explanations and discussions, and for understanding the translation text.

Conflict of Interest:

The author declares no conflict of interest.

Received:

Revised:

Published online:

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